

Supplementary Table ST5: Limitation Categories with Counts and Example Papers

Limitation Category	Prevalence	Description	Example Studies
Data-related	45.5% (45/99)	values, data quality issues	S14, S16, S30, S46, S56, S69, S70, S82, S89
Spatial	40.4% (40/99)	generalizability	S5, S9, S15, S23, S26, S34, S37, S45, S51, S58, S62
Extremes	30.3% (30/99)	extreme wind gusts	S3, S4, S14, S16, S21, S28, S35, S46, S51, S63, S68, S74, S78
Generalizability	35.4% (35/99)	time operations	S2, S9, S14, S22, S26, S27, S43, S45, S51, S63, S73, S88
Temporal	25.3% (25/99)	validation	S2, S14, S16, S23, S25, S29, S31, S33, S36, S56, S64, S78
Operational	20.2% (20/99)	forecaster trust	S5, S9, S14, S18, S26, S31, S37, S43, S52, S63, S84, S86
Methodological	18.2% (18/99)	comparisons	S16, S19, S28, S29, S31, S33, S40, S46, S56, S69, S89, S94
Computational	15.2% (15/99)	Large parameter counts, high training costs, inference latency	S5, S8, S9, S11, S24, S40, S48, S64, S79, S93, S99
Interpretability	12.1% (12/99)	Black-box nature, forecaster trust, lack of physical constraints	S1, S19, S20, S28, S31, S37, S38, S45, S68, S83, S84, S98